

EMPLOYEE MOTIVATION TECHNIQUES ADOPTED BY HR MANAGER IN ORGANIZATIONS: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO IT INDUSTRY IN DELHI NCR

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1. INTRODUCTION OF THE TOPIC

In recent years Human Resource Management has turned into a central part of an extensive number of IT organizations with one of their fundamental obligations being to furnish their employers with motivated employees (Sharma, 2006)[1]. Bratton and Gold (2012)[2] suggests that HRM is a key methodology which identifies with the management of business relations that underlines the increasing person's capabilities. This is noteworthy with regards to accomplishing a favorable competitive position, and it should be possible using projects, practices, and arrangements in Delhi. A noteworthy part of HR is to furnish in IT organizations with motivated employees who can result in higher job satisfaction and performance.

The point of this research is to distinguish the effect of HR practices on employee motivation and performance in Delhi NCR. With the end goal to accomplish the point of this research it's imperative that the accompanying points and destinations are featured; investigate the significance of HR, the significance of HR practices on authoritative yield, what factors influence job satisfaction in the work environment and to distinguish what persuades employees. 'The effect of HR practices on employee motivation and performance.' The requirement for improving Human resources management and methodologies has been proposed by the literature. For the most part, researchers concur that human resources are the primary hotspot for each organization. The primary targets of this examination are to the current condition of Human resources management in IT organizations, in addition, to demonstrate phase of development and usage in human resources management.

1.1.1 Employee Motivation Toolkit

Employees are the most fundamental part of any successful business. The more joyful your employees are at work, the more proficient your business stream will be it's as straightforward as that. In any case, with the goal for employees to be great at what they do, they should be motivated, drawn in, productive and successful at work. By and large, an organization culture and condition where employees can feel great and loose does the job in IT industry. Be that as it may, what happens when the general employee motivation begin to decrease even with great conditions set up? That is the place human resources supervisors become possibly the most

important factor. HR administrators are in charge of estimating and keeping up the positive temperament far reaching and are arbiters among employees and upper management, particularly in bigger organizations. This job isn't as simple as it might sound however with a bit of exertion and devotion, each association can have glad employees. Here are a couple of things HR chiefs can use to persuade employees.

1.1.2 Communication for the Win

It's important to understand that employees aren't just an unfortunate obligation. They're the most important part of a company. That is the reason you can't remove yourself from your employees. Rather, keep open communication with them and be straightforward when speaking with your employees consistently. If your employees know they can straightforwardly converse with you and offer their potential issues or issues without confronting repercussions, they'll feel calmer when they're at work. The conspicuous answer is to help them monetarily.

Be that as it may, they may likewise be supporting another person (a family for instance), or they may attempt to raise assets to satisfy one of their life-long dreams. These individual reasons spur individuals to work. What's more, to the opposite, on the off chance that they happen to have any troubles in their own lives, the odds are that it will ponder their job. On the off chance that you offer to enable them to defeat these regardless of whether it's a listening ear they'll without a doubt be thankful, and consequently, they'll turn out to be more motivated at work. Ensure that you provide insight and help to your employees at whatever point they require it, and you can be sure your employees will be more joyful and more motivated.

2. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This research aims at finding of the employee motivation methods and techniques by HR in IT organization. Along with it, this research has following objectives of study

- To identify the factors that employees motivation to perform at a high standard in IT industry in Delhi NCR.
- To determine factors that brings about a high level of job satisfaction among employees in order to engage employees to achieve organisational goals and reduces the rate of employee turnover.
- To examine the influence of training on an employee's work performance in an organization in Delhi NCR.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

➤ This research is motivating factors of human resources as a reason for increasing the quality of giving administrations at nearby level authorities. It will likewise make inferences that recognize the elements that will be a key for a target assessment of the performance level. Besides, it will clarify the significance and the impact of human resources about the need of evaluation, employee motivation with the end goal to satisfy their prerequisites which may prompt better administrations giving to the general society in Delhi-NCR.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rao (2008) [6] explored the cases that when employees work to the best of their abilities and do their work with energy, eagerness and high commitment the business will develop fundamentally and persistently. In general, each association has a similar sort of resources, for example, arrive, structures, materials, gear, and fund to work with, yet the main element that separates between business organizations is the HR factor. If the organizations utilize and utilize its human resource to the best potential preferred standpoint, there is next to no that can stop the association accomplishing its objectives and targets. The previous director of General Electric likewise trusts that human resources are the foundation of the association because of the way that they create and utilize technology; they contribute incredible ideas for product development and convey predominant client administrations, they gather, investigate and appropriate information, and they make and execute the system.

Nel et al. (2014)[7] studied that distinguishing the key factors that spur employees at work is vital for the association to perceive and understand the key motivational components that impact their employees' behavior and move can be made to enable the association to make proper and suitable techniques to persuade their employees to perform work at an abnormal state.

Nickson, (2013) [8] introduced the hospitality business tasks rely upon an able and administration situated work constraint. It is important for the hospitality industry to have compelling HR functions, for example, job examination, employee selection, training and development, remuneration management and motivational plans that are coordinated or connected with its vital plans or objectives with the end goal to enhance organizational performance principles, convey quality administration to clients, and keep up its competitiveness in the pursuit of organizational achievement.

McGuire and Jorgensen, (2010) [9] Looking back to the development of HR practices, in the mid-1970s, there was just a department called staff department which included the workforce in the association. In the late 70s, the world economy changed relentlessly, and organizations started to consider the work constrain as an important resource for their business activities and tasks. The idea of human resource management (HRM) started during the 1980s, and this idea developed and created throughout the following decade. In the course of the most recent 30 years, HRM has pulled into consideration crosswise over numerous fields because of its commitment to the viability and productivity of employee management. In the present worldwide economy, organizations are working in a dynamic and quick evolving condition. With the end goal to keep up competitive favourable position, accomplish organizational key objectives, and adjust and change to react rapidly to showcase needs and demands, it is vital for contemporary organizations to have HR experts or HR managers who have refined and progressed HRM skills and knowledge.

Boxall and Purcell (2011) [10] assert that HRM possibly adds to employee work performance in the association. The quality of employee work performance is dependent on a function of ability, motivation, and opportunity. This implies HR managers intercede to create employee ability, motivation and opportunity with the end goal to boost work performance in the association. Motivation alludes to outer and interior factors that impact employees to play out a particular undertaking or job well. One of the jobs of HR managers is to expand the level of employee motivation.

Wilton (2011)[11] explained the points out that it is vital for HR managers to configuration jobs, execute practices, direct methodology, and make a work domain to invigorate and urge employees to perform to their maximum capacity in the route wanted by the association. HR managers ought to understand natural and outward factors, for example, the budgetary motivator, recognition, job satisfaction and accomplishment that persuade workers and open the intensity of optional exertion in them. HR managers should focus on accommodate the common interests or blended thought processes of organizations and workers, and ensure the two employers and employees have adequate levels of the shared relationship with the end goal to keep up and maintain the stability of work performance. HRM alludes to each one of those activities including recruiting, planning work for, training and creating, assessing and fulfilling, directing and persuading employees in the association. HRM is the framework of techniques, strategies, methods, and practices for dealing with the relationship between employers and employees.

Boella and Goss-Turner, (2012) [12] Training is characterized as "the process of building up a staff part's knowledge, skills, and attitudes important to perform undertakings required for a position." Training and development can impact organizational performance likewise in the hospitality industry. This investigation is inspecting the impact of applicable training programs that employees ought to get with the end goal to build up the capacity of their work performance. If the association does not have a viable training and development program, it will fall behind as far as the ranges of abilities and knowledge required for the competitive

favorable position. Training and development is a major test that each association should address.

Mishra, M. N. (2009) [13] investigated are of the feeling that the rapid changes in cutting-edge innovation in the present workplace adjust the manner by which work is performed. Training is an interest in the work compels which positions itself for accomplishment later on in any hospitality association. The primary reason for training is to provide the workforce with the essential skills and knowledge required playing out a job adequately, and job training is a progressing process that counteracts old HR in the association and increment organizational productivity. Components that spur lodging employees to perform at elevated expectation levels are discussed in the literature in this section. Employee motivation is anything but another subject in HRM, and it has been characterized by unmistakable researchers in different fields and huge numbers of them give diverse definitions to employee motivation. Be that as it may, a considerable lot of these definitions have comparative ideas and thoughts. From the investigations of the economy, brain research, and human resources, motivation alludes to reasons or factors that energize, or influence people to carry on especially.

Pinder, (2014) [14] motivated likewise alludes to the inborn and outward elements that impact a person to act in certain ways or take certain activities. Motivation is a power (either natural or extraneous) that influences people to do what they do. This implies singular motivation is affected by both inside elements (counting individual needs and desires) and outside variables (organizational reward and pay). With regards to HRM, motivation is critical to organizational performance. The association can inspire their employees to work harder and be engaged with accomplishing organizational objectives. Persuading employees is tied in with utilizing distinctive noteworthy components to impact them in the way that makes them feel motivated to play out their errands with their best exertion, help their productivity levels, or complete their assignments at an exclusive expectation.

Nahavandi et al., (2014) [15] another motivation behind why the association puts more exertion into rousing employees is that an association with a motivated workforce presents change sooner than the association where its employees are demotivated. From a general point of view, every individual can be motivated. Be that as it may, every individual isn't motivated or affected by "similar things, in the meantime, for similar reasons, or with a similar intensity." Job satisfaction is characterized as "the attitudes and feelings people have about their work. Positive and good attitudes towards the job demonstrate job satisfaction. Negative and ominous attitudes towards the job show job dissatisfaction". Regularly, assurance is otherwise called job satisfaction. Confidence happens when employees feel their requirements are fulfilled or when they feel they accomplish something that has significance and esteem recognition in the workplace. Confidence or job satisfaction decreases when there is additionally demanding and unpleasant work, fewer relationships with the best management, and lacking remuneration and different prizes.

Chandan, (2009)[16] guaranteed that there is a relation between job satisfaction and the organizational reward system and reward plans, for example, pay, benefits, advancements and other budgetary benefits extraordinarily add to job satisfaction in the workplace. Job

satisfaction enhances when pay and advancement are viewed as reasonable and sensible; level with pay for equivalent work and decency in advancement. The second factor that impacts job satisfaction is simply the work. The idea of work prompts the feeling of satisfaction. Independence, flexibility, and attentiveness of job can vigorously add to job satisfaction.

4. RESEARCH METHDOLOGY

4.1 Pilot Study

This study is an ever increasing number of organizations from the international business condition, are beginning to think about their own employees as a more important resource than the budgetary capital or the physical resources. That is the reason the employee motivation is getting to be one of the fundamental concentrations among the organizations who need to keep up a competitive position in the market. Employee Motivation and motivation, as an instrument utilized for the expansion of human resource productivity development and association performance, it might take distinctive shapes, as indicated by the psychosocial profile of every employee. In this way, the managers should manufacture an individual relationship with their employees and endeavour to understand their assumptions about to what the company can offer at that point. The pilot study enables the researcher to familiarize himself with the administration of the instruments.

4.2 Statement of the Research Problem

The research entitled, A Critical Analysis of “Employee Motivation Methods and Techniques Adopted by HR Manager in Organization: with Special Reference to IT industry in Delhi-NCR”, the investigator adopted the following definitions for the terms used in this title.

4.3 Research Design and Strategies

This is the descriptive research. We follow with the design of Study followed with the data collection and management. After data collected we would explore and use descriptive study. We will follow the following way of data collection strategies

Primary Data Collection

Primary source is a source from where we collect first-hand information or original data on a topic. Data would be collected primarily form open and close-ended questionnaire that can justify The motivational theories are trying to explain how a certain behaviour can be started, how can it be sustained, driven in a certain direction and stopped when the said behaviour is no longer considered acceptable by the organization’s standards.

Secondary Data Collection

We have collected secondary data from the published statements of the firms, newspaper and articles. This is the minor part of this research but important as well. In this part data would be collected from the internet sites, journals, books, published articles, records of an organization. This type of data have been collected and recorded by another person or organization, sometimes for altogether different purposes.

4.4 Research Hypothesis

Primary Hypothesis: Motivational techniques being adopted by HR enhance employee's performance hence helps in organizational development.

Secondary Hypotheses:

1. HR's policy and strategy can increase performance of employees and organization growth simultaneously.
2. There are the motivating factors that have an impact on employee performance at the local areas and organization.
3. There would be significant Motivating factors impact employee performance improvement.

5. ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

Effectiveness of the HR Systems and Policies

The views of the firms with regard to the effectiveness of their HR systems and policies are presented here.

Table 5.1 Views on the Statement: 'The recruitment/selection procedure is effective and it serves the company's purpose'

The recruitment/selection procedure is effective and it serves the company			
	Purpose		
	Somewhat effective	Highly effective	Total
MNC Indian	1	4	5
	20.0%	80.0%	100.0%
Foreign	2	3	5
	40.0%	60.0%	100.0%
Total	3	7	10
	30.0%	70.0%	100.0%

Source: Survey Data

The perspectives of the firms with regard to the viability of the recruitment/selection procedures and whether it serves the purpose of the company are presented in Table 5.4. An analysis of the table demonstrates that a majority of seven (70 per cent) firms report that their recruitment/selection procedures are 'highly successful'

Table 5.2 Effectiveness of the communication system in retention and motivation of the employees

Communication system of the organization is effective in retaining and motivating the employee							
	Somewhat effective	Highly effective	Mean	S.D	Percentage Mean	Z value	p value
MNC Indian	3	2	4.40	.548	88.00	.000	1.000
	60.0%	40.0%					NS
Foreign	3	2	4.40	.548	88.00		
	60.0%	40.0%					
Total	6	4	4.40	.516	88.00		
	60.0%	40.0%					

Source: Survey Data

With regard to the viability of the communication system in retaining and motivating the employees (Table 4.6), the overall rating is at 88.0 per cent ($a = \pm .516$), which implies that the communication system is considered as 'highly viable' in retaining and motivating the employees. Among both the Indian and foreign MNCs, the rating of the adequacy is at 88.0 per cent ($cr = \pm .548$), which implies that both the types of MNCs consider the communication systems of their respective firms as 'highly powerful' in retaining and motivating their employees.

With regard to the viability of the reward and recognition policies of the firms in retaining and motivating the employees (Table 5.7), the overall rating of the adequacy is at 88.0 per cent ($o = \pm .966$), which implies that the firms consider their reward and recognition policies as 'highly compelling' in retaining and motivating the employees. The rating of the viability by Indian MNCs is at 92.0 per cent ($0 \pm .548$), which implies that they consider their policies as 'highly viable' and the rating by the foreign MNCs is at 84.0 per cent ($a = \pm 1.304$), which also implies that these firms consider their policies as 'highly powerful'.

5.3 Table: Effectiveness of the rewards and recognition policy in retention and motivation of the employees

	Somewhat ineffective	Somewhat effective	Highly effective	Mean	S.D	Percentage Mean	Z value	p value
MNC Indian	0	2	3	4.60	.548	92.00	.811	.841
	.0%	40.0%	60.0%					NS
Foreign	1	1	3	4.20	1.304	84.00		
	20.0%	20.0%	60.0%					
Total	1	3	6	4.40	.966	88.00		
	10.0%	30.0%	60.0%					

Source: Survey Data

Table 5.4 Effectiveness of the organizational culture in retention and motivation of the employees

Organizational culture is effective in the retention and motivation of the employees							
	Somewhat effective	Highly effective	Mean	S.D	Percentage Mean	Z value	p value
MNC Indian	3	2	4.60	.548	92.00	.60	.549
	60.0%	40.0%					NS
Foreign	3	2	4.40	.548	88.00		
	60.0%	40.0%					
Total	6	4	4.50	.527	90.00		
	60.0%	40.0%					

Source: Survey Data

With regard to the viability of the organizational culture in retaining and motivating the employees (Table 4.8), the overall rating of the adequacy is at 90.0 per cent ($a = \pm .527$), which implies that the firms consider their organizational cultures as 'highly viable' in retaining and motivating the employees. The rating of the adequacy by the Indian MNCs is at 92.0 per cent ($a = \pm .548$), which implies that they consider their policies as 'highly viable' and the rating by the foreign MNCs is at 88.0 per cent ($a = \pm .548$), which also implies that these firms consider their policies as 'highly successful'.

With regard to the adequacy of the performance appraisal system in retaining and motivating the employees (Table 5.9), the overall rating of the viability by the firms is at 88.0 per cent ($a = \pm .548$), which implies that the firms consider their performance appraisal systems as 'highly successful' in retaining and motivating the employees. The rating of the viability by both the Indian and foreign MNCs is at 88.0 per cent ($a = \pm .548$), which implies that both the types of MNCs consider their performance appraisal systems as 'highly viable'.

6. CONCLUSION

Here an attempt is made to recapitulate the major findings of the study, to recommend suitable suggestions on the basis of the findings and also to give directions for further research. The present study was carried out with the following specific objectives:

- To contextualize the emergence of ITES-BPO industry in India and to analyze the nature and composition of human resources in the ITES-BPO industry.
- To explore the correlates of motivation and/or demotivation of ITES-BPO employees and to enquire into the causes of growing dissatisfaction/frustration among the ITES-BPO employees.
- To examine the effectiveness of the HR practices adopted by ITES - BPO units having a direct bearing on the motivation/demotivation of ITES-BPO employees and to suggest

measures to improve employee motivation in the ITES-BPO industry.

- The study is based on the empirical evidence collected from ten sample ITES - BPO firms (five Indian MNCs and five foreign MNCs) and 406 employees constituting 1 per cent of the employee population under study. The researcher has used the Purposive Sampling Method to select the ten ITES-BPO firms. The study is conducted in the State of Delhi NCR .

Summary of the Findings

The major observations and findings of the study are:

- The variables ‘Adequate training for the current job,’ ‘Provision of as much ongoing training as needed,’ and ‘The training and development program of the company in general’ have a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the induction and training program.
- The variables ‘Variety in task,’ ‘Shift timings’ and ‘The number and duration of breaks’ significantly influence the satisfaction of the respondents towards the job description. While the variables ‘Variety in task’ and ‘The Number and duration of breaks’ are positively associated, the variable of ‘Shift timings’ is negatively associated with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the job description.
- The variables ‘Adequacy of the salary package for the work done,’ ‘Competitiveness of the salary package,’ and ‘Incentives and salary hikes’ have a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the salary and compensation package.
- Only the variable ‘Competitive and transparent work environment’ has a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the working conditions/environment and relationship with peers.
- The variables ‘The encouragement to speak freely at meeting/encouragement for open communication’ and ‘the supervisor’s concern about the professional and personal growth’ have a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the relationship with superiors.
- The variables ‘Transparency in the appraisal system,’ ‘Employee participation in appraisal system,’ ‘The objectivity in the appraisals,’ ‘Recognition of special initiatives and efforts at the time of appraisals,’ ‘The accuracy of the previous appraisals’ and ‘Viewing appraisals as a motivating tool’ have a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the performance appraisal system.
- Only the variable ‘Promotion policy is fair and transparent’ has a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the promotion policy.
- The variables ‘If I do good work, I can count on being promoted,’ ‘I am adequately recognized for my good work,’ ‘I am encouraged to take new initiatives/risks’ have a

significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the reward and recognition policy.

- The variables of ‘Company policies and procedures are open and transparent and create a positive work environment’, ‘Company is very open to ideas and suggestions given by the employees’ and ‘The company lives up to the promises made’ have a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the organizational culture.
- The variables ‘I have a clearly established career path’, ‘Viewing BPO sector as a long-term career option’ and ‘Having a dynamic career path is a must in order to retain the outstanding and highly-performing employees’ have a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards the career development initiatives.
- The correlates of ‘Satisfaction with the induction and training program’, ‘Satisfaction with the working conditions/environment’, ‘Satisfaction with the promotion policy’, ‘Satisfaction with the reward and recognition’ and ‘Satisfaction with the career development’ have a significant and positive association with the satisfaction of the respondents towards their overall level of satisfaction.
- Based on the factor analysis, the factors of job security, personal life, status, achievement, recognition for good work, opportunity for advancement, opportunity for growth, added responsibility, work itself, open and honest communication have emerged as the motivating factors for the employees of the Indian ITES-BPO industry and factors of company policy and administration, quality of supervision, inter-personal relationship with peers, inter-relationship with supervisors, inter-relationship with subordinates, salary, working conditions, personal human relationship, good corporate and brand image, global work environment can be considered as the hygiene or maintenance factors.

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